

VITAMIN D3 -EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY STUDIES FOR ORODISPERSIBLE TABLETS NOVEL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Vitamin D3 (Cholecalciferol) is a form of Vitamin D used in the treatment of specific medical conditions such as refractory rickets, hypoparathyroidism, and familial hypophosphatemia, as well as osteoporosis and chronic kidney disease. The main objective of the present study was to the preformulation studies were performed to know the physico-chemical and mechanical properties of Vitamin D3 (Cholecalciferol) for formulation development of ODTs. The drug-excipient compatibility studies were conducted to characterize the drug Vitamin D3 present in Orodispersible tablets (ODTs). The safety, efficacy, quality and stability of a formulation are major concepts of any API development process. In API development process, a detailed characterization of the API and other formulation components is usually carried out during the preformulation stage. Preformulation, formulation and evaluation of Vitamin D3 to avoid problems associated with conventional delivery system such as limited permeation, low dissolution and bioavailability and also to improve bioavailability and Vitamin

D3 is an essential nutrient that plays a crucial role in calcium homeostasis, bone health, and immune function. In the present study that the compatibility was assessed by, FTIR spectroscopy, and melting point apparatus, precompression parameters and powder flow properties. Results showed that physical mixtures of Vitamin D3 and various excipients as lactose monohydrate, mannitol, microcrystalline cellulose as diluents, and sodium starch glycolate, croscarmellose sodium, and crospovidone as superdisintegrants agents were evaluated for preformulation studies parameters. It was concluded that the drug Vitamin D3 was found to be compatible with various excipients which were selected for the formulation development of the Vitamin D3 ODTs NDDS. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage and is an important factor in the NDDS (Novel Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

KEYWORDS: Vitamin D3 (Cholecalciferol), Bone Health, Compatibility, Excipients, Development, Preformulation, Novel Drug Delivery Systems.

INTRODUCTION

Background^[1-12]

Most individuals naturally generate adequate amounts of vitamin D through ordinary dietary intake of vitamin D (in some foods like eggs, fish, and cheese) and natural photochemical conversion of the vitamin D3 precursor 7-dehydrocholesterol in the skin via exposure to sunlight. Vitamin D, beyond its well-known role in calcium and phosphate homeostasis, is pivotal in modulating the immune system. It influences both innate and adaptive immunity and has been implicated in the pathogenesis of several autoimmune diseases, including type 1 diabetes, multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, and inflammatory bowel disease. Moreover, adequate vitamin D levels are associated with a reduced risk of acute respiratory tract infections, and emerging evidence suggests a link between severe vitamin D deficiency and increased COVID-19-related mortality. Endogenously, vitamin D is synthesized in the skin upon exposure to ultraviolet B (UVB) radiation, converting 7-dehydrocholesterol to cholecalciferol (vitamin D₃). This is subsequently hydroxylated in the liver to 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D], the primary circulating form, and then in the kidneys to the active form, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D [1,25(OH)₂D]. Serum 25(OH)D levels between 20–50ng/mL are considered optimal, while levels below 12ng/mL indicate severe deficiency. Despite the body's ability to synthesize vitamin D, factors such as limited sun exposure and dietary intake often necessitate supplementation to maintain adequate levels.

Vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol) is preferred over D₂ (ergocalciferol) due to its superior absorption and efficacy. However, its lipophilic nature poses formulation challenges, particularly in developing aqueous-based dosage forms. Traditional supplements, including oil-based solutions, soft capsules, and injections, may not be suitable for all populations, especially those with swallowing difficulties. Therefore, there's a need for alternative delivery systems that enhance bioavailability and patient compliance. Although solid dosage forms i.e. tablets are most acceptable dosage patients often experience difficulty in swallowing conventional tablets when water is not available nearby. And in case of, pediatric and geriatric patients may also encounter inconvenience in swallowing it leading to patient's incompliance. In such, patients and to increase the compliance orally disintegrating tablets (ODTs) are a perfect fit for these patients as they immediately release the active drug, when placed on the tongue, by rapid disintegration, along with dissolution.

Pharmaceutical Research Paths^[13-83]

Pharmaceutical research is characterized by having both a natural source and synthetic source for primary active raw materials and excipients, each source is mainly prepared to the effectiveness and safety of the drug.

The Pharmaceutical Research Paths include: Pharmacognosy deals with natural sources of drug, Pharmaceutical Chemistry specializes in synthetic sources of drug, Pharmaceutics specializes in designing of pharmaceutical dosage forms and drug delivery systems from natural and synthetic sources of active pharmaceutical ingredients and excipients that help in developing dosage forms and drug delivery systems.

The Pharmaceutical Research Paths link steps are manufacturing and development of drug according to the standard parameters evaluation such as physiochemical properties, preformulation, formulation, evaluation, drug stability, Pharmaceutical analysis, pre-clinical, post-clinical stages, pre-marketing, post-marketing, Pharmacovigilance, Pharmacoeconomics, Pharmacy Management, Pharmacology, Toxicology, Therapeutics, Pharmaceutical Care, Health Care, Advanced Industrial Pharmacy, Biopharmaceutics and Pharmacokinetics, Advanced Clinical Pharmacokinetics, Pharmaceuticals Cosmetics, Pharmaceutical Biotechnology, Drug Design, Pharmacy Law and Ethics, Pharmacogenomics, Good Manufacturing Practice, and Good Pharmacy Practice etc.

All of these Pharmaceutical Research Paths are interconnected, and whenever the link between them is made in a scientific relationship and the goal of pharmaceutical care is achieved gradually according to plan of a scientific pharmaceutical research path.

Pharmaceutical Research Paths are the scientific methods through which the scientific relationship between the pharmaceutical team, research, supervisor or specialist researcher, the scientific research materials, equipment's, scientific institution, pharmaceutical companies, reference standards, and the goals of pharmaceutical research improve and development of community services of pharmaceutical care and health care.

Pharmaceutical Scientists are considering natural sources and medicinal herbs in the pharmaceutical industry an important part of drug development because natural sources of drugs have properties that are greater than industrial sources of drugs in NDDS. And the pharmaceutical industry strategies depend on the development of different pharmaceutical dosage forms and recent novel drug delivery systems. Using medicinal herbs and natural sources as important goals of drug development. It is part of the art of innovation in drug development with different of novel drug delivery systems and pharmaceutical care for patients and society, it's the basic of development of the new pharmaceutical industry by developing different novel drug delivery systems from different sources.

Preformulation Studies^[84-156]

The safety, efficacy, quality and stability of a formulation are major concepts of any API development process. In API development process, a detailed characterization of the API and other formulation components is usually carried out during the preformulation stage. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage and is an important factor in the ADDS (Advanced Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

One of the objectives of this study is to development of drug delivery systems by building scientific pharmaceutical research information depend on formulation scientists to join the knowledge and experience as well as experimental and practical results of this study with regard to information in previous studies, and approved references. It was found to be that the most important concepts and basics of preformulation studies such as definitions, methods, conclusion, idea, and types of pharmaceutical analysis techniques using in evaluation of preformulation studies parameters, in this study that we focused on developing drug delivery

systems and linking the formulation development to establish the basics of pharmaceutical research in studying the drug-excipient compatibility, dug with various excipients, which is important for the safety, effectiveness, quality, formulation, stability, bioavailability, and pharmacokinetics of the drug etc.

Preformulation research were evolved in 1950. It is defined as the phase of research and development in which preformulation studies characterize physical and chemical properties of a drug molecule in order to develop safe, effective, bioavailability and stable dosage form. In preformulation studies, physicochemical properties of drug molecules are characterized either alone or in combination with excipients. Preformulation is the first step in the rational formulation of an active pharmaceutical ingredient (API).

Preformulation Study Includes: Determination of physical chemical properties of API substance with the goal of developing a new drug which is safe stable and efficacious, each API, has intrinsic chemical and physical properties that were considered prior to the development of pharmaceutical formulation, the purpose of preformulation study is to generate useful information for the formulator in the development of stable and bioavailable dosage form, inappropriate preformulation study results in poor stability of active ingredients increase the overall cost of development and increased development time, preformulation studies help to fortify the pharmaceutical scientific foundation of the guidance, provide regulatory relief and conserve resources in the drug development and evaluation process, enhance public safety standards, improve product quality, promote the implementation of new technologies, aids policy development and regulatory decision making and after compiling all data it is transferred to the development pharmacist and for the day work on formulation of dosage form.

Preformulation Study Objectives: To establish the Physico-chemical parameters of a new API entity, determine its kinetics and stability, establish its compatibility with common excipients, it provides insights into how drug products should be processed and stored to ensure their quality, estimate problem may arise during formulation that is stability problem poor *in-vivo* dissolution, poor bioavailability, to interpret BCS classification of drugs and its significance and develop optimal drug delivery system.

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Study: The primary objective of this investigation was to identify a stable storage condition for API in solid state and identification of compatible

excipients for its formulation. Incompatibilities are major concerns in formulation development. Selection of the proper excipient during preformulation studies is of prime importance.

Dosage Forms: DF contain API and pharmaceutical excipients, which are intended to generate an ideal formulation and manufacturability of pharmaceutical products, thereby enabling a much safer and more effective administration. Pharmaceutical excipients are ideally inactive and have no impact on the stability or therapeutic effect of the active ingredient. On the other hand, there are studies that have presented that some pharmaceutical excipients are just allegedly described as inactive ingredient. Some pharmaceutical excipients have the capacity to affect API, efficacy by affecting its pharmacokinetics. Excipients can affect the physical and chemical form of pharmaceuticals by several factors such as hydrogen bond interaction, polymorphic conversion, and others. Accordingly, drug-excipient compatibility should be conducted so as to determine any drug-excipient interactions that may obstruct the stability, bioavailability, and manufacturability of pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Importance of Drug-Excipient Compatibility

Studies of active pharmaceutical ingredient (API)-excipient compatibility represent an important study in the preformulation stage of the development of new dosage forms, stability of the dosage form can be maximized, any physical or chemical interaction between API, and excipient can affect bioavailability and stability of drug, it helps to avoid the surprise problem, by performing drug excipient compatibility studies (DECS) we can know the possible reaction before formulating final dosage form, DECS data is essential for IND (investigational new drug) submission, and now, USFDA has made it compulsory to submit DECS data for any new coming formulation before its approval.

The potential physical and chemical interactions between an API, and the excipients can affect the chemical nature, the stability and bioavailability of the former and, consequently, its therapeutic efficacy and safety, solid dosage forms are generally less stable than their API components and despite the importance of API-excipient compatibility testing, there is no universally accepted protocol to assess such interactions.

Pharmaceutical Excipients: Excipients are additive substances used to improve the bulkiness, disintegration, dissolution rate, and bioavailability of a formulation etc. Different dosage

forms like powders, granules, capsules, tablets, oral liquids, injectable products, implants, eye products, nasal products, inhalers, topical creams, ointments, gels, transdermal patches and suppositories etc, contains different types of excipients. To make it acceptable and compatible various pharmaceutical excipients are added in pharmaceutical dosage form for their direct therapeutic action, manufacturing process, to protect, support or enhance stability, for bioavailability or patient compliance. These must be physiologically and chemically stable, must not have any incompatibility with the API, and must meet the standards of regulatory requirements.

Evaluation of Drug-Excipient Compatibility

The compatibility study of API and excipients is important to predict the stability of the API, in the final pharmaceutical product. It's the first time that API was compatible with excipients promoted physical and chemical compatibility studies was achieved by thermal and non-thermal methods. As a part of preformulation study, a compatibility study of API with the other excipients was carried out using physical blends in analytical techniques for the evaluation of drug-excipient interactions. The most commonly used pharmaceutical analytical techniques include, thermal techniques such as Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Isothermal Microcalorimetry (IMC) and Hot stage microscopy (HSM) etc, and non-thermal techniques such as UV-Visible Spectrophotometric (UV), Infrared, Near-Infrared and Raman Spectroscopy (FT-IR), (NIR), Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD), Solid-State Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy (ssNMR), Microscopic techniques: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Chromatographic techniques: Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC), and High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) etc.

Preformulation Parameters: According to dosage form of API, mainly solid state, particle size, shape, pKa, pH determination, common ion effect, temperature, partition coefficient, solubility studies, dissolution rate, melting point, powder flow properties, crystallinity, polymorphism, hygroscopicity, stability study and drug-excipient compatibility etc. While other dosage forms according to important of preformulation parameters used in study before start in development of formulation.

Drug-excipient compatibility and formulation stability are not depended on API only but also its affected by excipient. Excipient play important role in dosage form but side by side it also increases compatibility problem so proper selection of excipient is very important in

development of formulation. Incompatibility can be result mainly in any of following changes: Changes in organoleptic properties, changes in dissolution performance, decrease in potency, and increase in degradation rate etc.

Drug excipient physicochemical characterization is a systematic approach towards design of therapeutically active and stable dosage forms. The rapid advancements in novel drug delivery systems development have led to an interest by formulation scientists in the role and functionality of the excipients.

In the present study, it was proposed to Vitamin D3 -excipient compatibility studies of the safety, efficacy, quality and stability of a formulation are major concepts of any API development process. In API development process, a detailed characterization of the API and other formulation components is usually carried out during the preformulation stage, with commonly different excipients using for formulation development of Vitamin D3 Orodispersible tablets NDDS. The most common and preferable route of drug administration is through the oral route.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Vitamin D3 and all raw materials used in the preformulation and formulation including active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), excipients, and analytical reagents were obtained as a gift sample from (Modern Pharma Pharmaceutical Industry Company - Yemen).

As shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Materials Used.

NO	Name of Materials
1	Vitamin D3
2	Crospovidone
3	Sodium Starch Glycolate
4	Croscarmellose Sodium
5	Avicel 102
6	Mannitol
7	PVP K30
8	Sodium Lauryl Sulfate
9	Aerosil 200
10	Magnesium Stearate
11	Aspartame
12	Orange Flavor
13	Distilled Water
14	Sodium Hydroxide

15	Monobasic Potassium Phosphate
16	Potassium Bromide
17	Acetonitrile

Equipment

All equipment used are listed in Table Error! No text of specified style in document.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.: **List of Instruments.**

NO	Instruments
1	Melting Point Apparatus
2	FTIR Spectrophotometer
3	UV-VIS Spectrophotometer
4	pH Meter
5	Density tester
6	Moisture tester
7	Electronic Balance

Evaluation of Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies Methods^[140-219]

Table 3: Vitamin D3 Data.

Characterization of Vitamin D3			
Vitamin D3 Structure and 3D Conformer			
Chemical Structure	(3 β , 5Z, 7E)-9, 10-secocholesta-5, 7,10(19)-trien-3-ol	Appearance	Fine, white to off-white and odorless crystalline powder.
Chemical Formula	C₂₇H₄₄O	Drug Solubility	Solubility: is a fat soluble Vitamin that is practically insoluble in water. Melting Point: 83-86 °C.
Molecular Weight	384.64g/mol	BCS	Class-II Drug

Drug Action and Use	<p>Vitamin D3 is a form of Vitamin D used in the treatment of specific medical conditions such as refractory rickets, hypoparathyroidism, and familial hypophosphatemia, as well as osteoporosis and chronic kidney disease.</p> <p>A medication found in many nutritional supplements and multivitamins that is used to treat conditions related to low vitamin D levels.</p> <p>The <i>in vivo</i> synthesis of the predominant two biologically active metabolites of vitamin D occurs in two steps. The first hydroxylation of vitamin D3 cholecalciferol (or D2) occurs in the liver to yield 25-hydroxyvitamin D while the second hydroxylation happens in the kidneys to give 1, 25-dihydroxyvitamin D. These vitamin D metabolites subsequently facilitate the active absorption of calcium and phosphorus in the small intestine, serving to increase serum calcium and phosphate levels sufficiently to allow bone mineralization.</p>		
Vitamin D3 Pharmacokinetics			
Drug Absorption	<p>Cholecalciferol is readily absorbed from the small intestine if fat absorption is normal. Moreover, bile is necessary for absorption as well. In particular, recent studies have determined aspects about the absorption of vitamin D, like the fact that:</p> <p>a) the 25-hydroxyvitamin D metabolite of cholecalciferol is absorbed to a greater extent than the nonhydroxy form of cholecalciferol, b) the quantity of fat with which cholecalciferol is ingested does not appear to largely affect its bioavailability, and c) age does not apparently effect vitamin D cholecalciferol.</p>	Drug Distribution	<p>Volume of Distribution: Stored in fat, muscle, liver. studies have determined that the mean central volume of distribution of administered cholecalciferol supplementation in a group of 49 kidney transplant patients was approximately 237 L</p> <p>Protein binding: The protein binding documented for cholecalciferol is 50 to 80%. Specifically, in the plasma, vitamin D3 (from either diet or the skin) is bound to vitamin D-binding protein (DBP) produced in the liver, for transport to the liver. Ultimately, the form of vitamin D3 reaching the liver is 25-hydroxylated, and such 25-hydroxycholecalciferol is bound to DBP (α2-globulin) whilst circulating in the plasma.</p>
Drug Metabolism	<p>Within the liver, cholecalciferol is hydroxylated to calcifediol (25-hydroxycholecalciferol) by the</p>	Drug Excretion	<p>Route of Elimination: It has been observed that administered cholecalciferol and its</p>

	enzyme vitamin D-25-hydroxylase. At the kidney, calcifediol subsequently serves as a substrate for 1-alpha-hydroxylase, yielding calcitriol (1,25-dihydroxycholecalciferol), the biologically active form of vitamin D3.		metabolites are excreted primarily in the bile and feces. Clearance: Studies have determined that the mean clearance value of administered cholecalciferol supplementation in a group of 49 kidney transplant patients was approximately 2.5 L/day.
The Elimination Half-Life (T_{1/2})	At this time, there have been resources that document the half-life of cholecalciferol as being about 50 days while other sources have noted that the half-life of calcitriol (1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D3) is approximately 15 hours while that of calcidiol (25-hydroxyvitamin D3) is about 15 days.	Availability	Tablets: 10000unit Capsules: 10000unit Capsules: 100000unit Capsules: 25000unit Capsules: 5000unit Tablets: 10mg Tablets: 2000iu Tablets: 400unit Tablet, Chewable.

Table 4: Pharmaceutical Excipients Data.

Nonproprietary Name	Synonyms	Functional Category	Incompatibilities
Croscarmellose Sodium (Ac-Di-Sol)	Cellulose, carboxymethyl ether, sodium salt, crosslinked.	Tablet and capsule disintegrant.	Incompatible with strong acids or with soluble salts of iron and some other metals such as aluminum, mercury, and zinc.
Crospovidone (PVPP)	1-Ethenyl-2-pyrrolidinone homopolymer	Tablet disintegrant.	Compatible with most organic and inorganic pharmaceutical ingredients.
Sodium Starch Glycolate (Explotab)	Sodium carboxymethyl starch	Tablet and capsule disintegrant.	Incompatible with ascorbic acid.
Microcrystalline Cellulose (Avicel PH102)	Cellulose	Adsorbent, suspending agent, tablet and capsule diluent; tablet disintegrant.	Incompatible with strong oxidizing agents.
Mannitol (Emprove)	Mannitol	Diluent, plasticizer, sweetening agent, tablet and capsule diluent, therapeutic	Incompatible with may be salted out by potassium chloride or sodium chloride.

		agent, tonicity agent.	Sodium cephalosporin. xylitol infusion and may form complexes with some metals such as aluminum, copper, and iron.
Magnesium Stearate (magnesium salt)	Octadecanoic acid magnesium salt	Tablet and capsule lubricant.	Incompatible with strong acids, alkalis, and iron salts.
PVP K30	E1201, Kollidon, Plasdone, polyvidone, polyvinylpyrrolidone, PVP; 1-vinyl-2-pyrrolidinone polymer.	Disintegrant, tablet binder.	compatible in solution with a wide range of inorganic salts, natural and synthetic resins, and other chemicals.
Aspartame	3-Amino-N-(α -carboxyphenethyl) succinamic acid N-methyl ester; 3-Amino-N-(α -methoxycarbonylphenethyl) succinamic acid;	Sweetening agent. It enhances flavor systems and can be used to mask some unpleasant taste characteristics; the approximate sweetening power is 180–200 times that of sucrose.	incompatible with dibasic calcium phosphate and also with the lubricant magnesium stearate. Reactions between aspartame and sugar alcohols.
Aerosil	Aerosil; Cab-O-Sil, Cab-OSil M-5P, colloidal silica, fumed silica, fumed silicon dioxide, SAS, silica colloidalis anhydrica	Adsorbent; anticaking agent glidant; viscosity-increasing agent	Incompatible with diethylstilbestrol preparations.

According to Vitamin D3 and excipients data as shown in Tables 3 and 4, it was selected that the different excipients to preformulation study with Vitamin D3 in the present study,

Drug Identification Test

Determination of The Organoleptic Properties

The organoleptic properties like color, odor and taste of the API were evaluated. Color a small quantity of Vitamin D3 was taken in a butter paper and viewed in well illuminated place. Taste and odor very less quantity of Vitamin D3 was used to assess the taste with the help of tongue as well as smelled to get odor. The organoleptic properties of the API substance were assessed.

Solubility Study

Solubility is a critical physicochemical parameter that directly influences drug absorption, bioavailability, and therapeutic efficacy. Poor aqueous solubility can significantly hinder formulation development, leading to suboptimal drug delivery and potential clinical failure.

An initial solubility screening of Vitamin D3 was carried out at room temperature (25°C) using various aqueous and non-aqueous solvent systems. This essential preformulation analysis provides critical data for optimal solvent and excipient selection in formulation development. This comprehensive solubility assessment establishes fundamental data for subsequent formulation optimization work as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Solubility Specification of Drugs.

Descriptive Term	Parts of Solvent Required for 1 Part of Solute:
Very Soluble	Less than 1
Freely Soluble	From 1 to 10
Soluble	From 10 to 30
Sparingly Soluble	From 30 to 100
Slightly Soluble	From 100 to 1000
Very Slightly Soluble	From 1000 to 10000
Practically Insoluble, or Insoluble	Greater than or equal to 10,000.

Preformulation Studies

Preformulation studies are initiated to define the physical and chemical properties of the agent. The key goals of preformulation studies are to ensure the delivery of drug product with acceptable stability, bioavailability, and manufacturability.

Melting Point Determination of Vitamin D3

Melting Point: Melting point of the R **Vitamin D3** was determined by capillary method; one sided closed capillary filled with drug and put into the Melting Point Apparatus. Temperature was noted at which solid drug changed into liquid.

Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies

A physical mixture including **Vitamin D3** and excipient was created in a 1:1 ratio, and it was subjected to analytical techniques such as FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR, of both pure drug and physical mixes were obtained, and the spectra of the both drug and mixture of excipient with drug were compared to look for any incompatibilities.

FTIR Spectroscopy Study

FTIR study KBr-disc method was used to record the FTIR spectra and KBr pellets were made in 1:100 ratio of sample and KBr. FTIR spectra was recorded using FTIR spectrum in a range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} . Different functional groups of test compound for distinctive vibrational frequencies are identified using FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR spectra were used for the investigation of interaction in the physical mixture of API and excipient through shifting of peaks to lower or higher wavenumbers and appearance or disappearance of characteristic peaks of functional groups for pure API in physical mixture. FTIR spectroscopic study was performed to check the compatibility between API, and different excipients in amount (5mg:5mg) as ratio (1:1) as shown in Table 5. The FTIR spectra of a API alone and API with excipients were obtained by KBr method and compared with the standard FTIR spectrum of the pure API. Infrared spectrophotometer is not only used for determining the compatibility of excipients with the APIs, but also for API identification.

Preparation of IR Samples

The sample was determined by the disc method. Triturate 5mg of the substance to be examined with 300-400 mg of finely powdered and dried potassium bromide R or potassium chloride R. Each excipient was mix with Vitamin D3 equally then of potassium bromide is added to the mixture. Carefully grind the mixture, spread it uniformly in a suitable die, and submit it to a pressure of about 800 MPa (8 t $\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). Then the tablets were inserted to the device and the Infrared spectra was recorded at mild-infrared light in wavenumber range of 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} . After that the spectra were compared with the reference.

Infrared Spectral Study of Samples in Room Condition

Compatibility studies were performed by preparing blend of different excipients with Vitamin D3 in room condition as shown in Table 6.

Infrared Spectral Study of Samples after Stored Two Weeks

Compatibility studies were performed by preparing blend of different excipients with drug and stored at 40°C \pm 2°C /75 \pm 5%RH for two weeks. The blend was evaluated after two weeks for changes like caking, liquefaction, discoloration and odor formation and by IR spectra. The drug excipient compatibility studies as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: The Drug and Excipients Compatibility Studies.

Sample Code	Drug with Excipients	Ratio (Drug: Excipient)
1	Vitamin D3	1
2	Crospovidone + Vitamin D3	1:1
3	Croscarmellose Sodium + Vitamin D3	1:1
4	Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG) + Vitamin D3	1:1
5	Aspartame + Vitamin D3	1:1
6	Orange Flavor + Vitamin D3	1:1
7	PVP K30 + Vitamin D3	1:1
8	Avicel + Vitamin D3	1:1
9	Mannitol + Vitamin D3	1:1
10	Aerosil 200 + Vitamin D3	1:1
11	Stearic acid + Vitamin D3	1:1
12	Lactose monohydrate + Vitamin D3	1:1
13	Strawberry + Vitamin D3	1:1

Pre-Compression Evaluation of The Powder

Micrometric Properties

Angle of Repose (θ)

Angle of repose is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of the powder and horizontal plane. The frictional force in a loose powder or granules can be measured by angle of repose as shown in Table 7.

$$\tan \theta = h / r$$

$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$ Where, θ is the angle of repose, h is the height of pile, r is the radius of the base of pile.

Table 7: Relationship Between Angle of Repose and Flow Properties.

Flow Property	Angle of Repose
Excellent	<25
Good	25-30
Passable	40-30
Very Poor	>40

Bulk Density

Bulk density is defined as the mass of a powder divided by the bulk volume. The bulk density of a powder depends primarily on particle size distribution, particle shape, and the tendency of the particles to adhere to one another.

$$\text{LBD} = \frac{\text{Weight of the powder (m)}}{\text{Volume of the packing (vo)}}$$

Tapped Density

The measuring cylinder containing a known mass of blend was tapped for a fixed time. The minimum volume (V_t) occupied in the cylinder and the weight (M) of the blend was measured. The tapped density (ρ_t) was calculated using the following formula.

$$\rho_t = M / V_t$$

Compressibility Index

The compressibility index of the granules was determined by Carr's compressibility index as shown in Table 8.

(%) Carr's Index can be calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Carr's Index (\%)} = \text{TBD} - \text{LBD} / \text{TBD} \times 100$$

Hausner Ratio

Hausner ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \rho_t / \rho_d$$

Where ρ_t is tapped density and ρ_d is bulk density. Lower Hausner ratio (<1.25) indicates better flow properties than higher ones (>1.25).

Table 8: Grading of the Powders for Their Flow Properties According to Carr's Index.

Compressibility Index	Flow Properties
5-15	Excellent
12-16	Good
18-21	Fair to Passable
23-35	Poor
33-38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identification Test

There are many of identification tests used in **Vitamin D3** identification. We used Melting point, IR spectrum.

Melting Point Determination of Vitamin D3

Melting point of pure Vitamin D3 was determined by open capillary method. The capillary tube was closed at one end by fusion and was filled with Vitamin D3 by repeated tapings. The capillary tube was placed in a digital melting point apparatus. The instrument was set to

automatically increase the temperature of the heating bath. The rise in temperature was viewed through screen. The temperature at which the drug started melting was recorded. The melting point range of Vitamin D3 was identical to reference melting point stated in MP (83–86°C). The sample started to melt at 83°C, and turned into liquid at 84°C, indicating that the sample used is pure. That reading has stated in melting point tester.as shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Results of Melting Point of Vitamin D3.

Test	Temp Rang Analyzed (Melting)	Results
Test I Vitamin D3	(83–86°C)	84°C
Test II Vitamin D3	(83–86°C)	84°C

Preformulation Tests of Powder

Organoleptic Properties

The organoleptic properties of Vitamin D3 were shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Organoleptic Properties of Vitamin D3.

Tests	Specification	Observation
Color	Non-hygroscopic, White Crystals	Non-hygroscopic, White Crystals
Odor	Odorless	Odorless
Taste	Bitter	Bitter

The organoleptic properties like color, odor and taste of the API were evaluated. The color of Vitamin D3 was found to be a white crystal, no characteristic odor was observed in the study and the taste was found to be bitter. Vitamin D3 showed similar color, taste and odor as per IP specification as shown in Table 10.

Characterization of Vitamin D3 by FTIR

FT-IR spectral studies of Vitamin D3 indicated that the drug is compatible with all the excipients. The FT-IR spectrum of physical mixture showed all the characteristic peaks of Vitamin D3, thus conforming that no interaction of drug occurred with the components of the physical mixture of drug with excipients as shown in Figures (1-13) and Tables (11-23).

Fig. 1: FTIR Spectra of Pure Vitamin D3 STD.

Table 11: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Pure Vitamin D3.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm^{-1})	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150

Fig. 2: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Crospovidone.

Table 12: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 and Crospovidone.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm^{-1})	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150

Fig. 3: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with CCS.

Table 13: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 and CCS.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ Croscarmellose Sodium	3400	1610	2900	1100

Fig. 4: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Strawberry.

Table 14: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with Strawberry.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ Strawberry	3398	1595	2895	1140

Fig. 5: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Asprtame.

Table 15: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with Asprrtame.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850- 3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ Aspartame	3395	1575	2890	1140

Fig. 6: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Lactose Monohydrate.

Table 16: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with Lactose Monohydrate.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ + Lactose	3300	1550	2890	1100

Fig. 7: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with PVPK30.

Table 17: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with PVPK30.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm^{-1})	3200-3600	1500-1600	1200-1350	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ PVPK30	3500	1550	2890	1130

Fig. 8: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with SSG.

Table 18: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with SSG.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm^{-1})	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ SSG	3390	1575	2890	1140

Fig. 9: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with MCC.

Table 19: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with MCC.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ Avicel 102	3390	1575	2895	1145

Fig. 10: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Mannitol.

Table 20: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with Mannitol.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3400	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ Mannitol	3300	1550	2950	1100

Fig. 11: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Orange Flavor.

Table 21: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with Orange Flavor.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	1640-1680	1500-1600	1200-1350	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	1668.08	1545.97	1218.91	1121.61
Vitamin D3+ Orange Flavor	1668.15	1545.46	1219.82	1121.36

Fig. 12: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Stearic Acid.

Table 22: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with Stearic Acid.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3 + Stearic acid	3390	1570	2890	1145

Fig. 13: FTIR Spectra of Vitamin D3 with Aerosil 200.

Table 23: Results of FTIR Spectrum of Physical Mixture Fresh and Stored of Vitamin D3 with Aerosil 200.

Specific Functional Groups	Alcohol C-OH Stretching	Aromatic C=C Stretching	C-H Stretching	C-O Stretching
The Mid-IR Region (cm ⁻¹)	3200-3600	1500-1600	2850-3000	1000-1150
Vitamin D3	3400	1580	2900	1150
Vitamin D3+ Aerosil	3410	1570		1140

Solubility Study

The dissolution characteristics of Vitamin D3 were systematically investigated in multiple solvent systems at ambient temperature (25±1°C). The study employed a dropwise addition method with continuous agitation to determine saturation points, with solubility categorization according to USP standards. The Solubility studies of drug revealed that Vitamin D3 is practically insoluble in water, freely soluble in ethanol (96 %), soluble in trimethylpentane and in fatty oils. As shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Table 24: Solubility Study of Vitamin D3.

Material	Test	Specification	Observation
Vitamin D3	Solubility	Practically insoluble in water, freely soluble in ethanol (96 %), soluble in trimethylpentane and in fatty oils. It is sensitive to air, heat and light. Solutions in solvents without an antioxidant are unstable and are to be used immediately. A reversible isomerization to pre-cholecalciferol takes place in solution, depending on temperature and time. The activity is due to both compounds.	Vitamin D3 is practically insoluble in water, freely soluble in ethanol (96%), soluble in trimethylpentane and in fatty oils.

Micrometric Properties of Vitamin D3

The powder of Vitamin D3 was evaluated for the following parameters such as angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, compressibility index and Hausner's ratio. The angle of repose of Vitamin D3 was found to be 36, which indicated Passable flow property. The bulk density was found to be 0.286.(g/ml), the tapped density was found to be 0.357 (g/ml). The Compressibility index was found to be 19.9%, which indicates fair flowability. The Hausner ratio was found to be 1.25. The results as shown in Tables 25 and 26.

Table 25: Micrometric properties of Vitamin D3.

Raw material	Bulk Vol	Tapp Vol	Bulk D (g/ml)	Tapp D (g/ml)	Bulkiness
Vitamin D3	35	28	0.286	0.357	3.50

Table 26: Evaluation of Precompression Parameters of Vitamin D3 Powder Blend.

Raw material	Voids	Porosity (%)	Compressibility index (%)	Hausner Ratio	Angle of Repose(θ)	Evaluation of Angle of Repose
Vitamin D3	7.0	20.0	19.9	1.25	36.0	Passable

CONCLUSION

The compatibility studies of physical mixtures of Vitamin D3 with different used excipients such as lactose monohydrate, mannitol, microcrystalline cellulose as diluents, and sodium starch glycolate, croscarmellose sodium, and crospovidone as superdisintegrants were investigated by FTIR it was detected that there was no variation or minor deviation in the characteristic peaks in FTIR spectroscopy. The Vitamin D3 formulations prepared were evaluated for precompression parameters and powder flow properties which were found to be within limits. It was concluded that the drug Rivaroxaban was found to be compatible with various excipients which were selected for the formulation development of the Vitamin D3 ODTs. Formulation scientist from his experience and knowledge have to significantly in the preformulation study stage and is an important factor in the NDDS (Novel Drug Delivery Systems) product development process.

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